

TAXONOMIC STUDY OF SOME COMMON RANIDS OF BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

A research work was conducted during the period of March to December 2008 to observe the taxonomic parameters of some selected common ranids of Bangladesh. The specimens were collected from different areas of the country. For convenience of observation only four species of the family Ranidae, i.e., *Euphyctis cyanophlyctis*, *Fejervarya limnocharis*, *Hylarana typhehensis* and *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* were studied. Tibio-tarsus articulation reached beyond the eye in *F. limnocharis* and *H. tigerinus*, in *E. cyanophlyctis* up to the eye and in *H. typhehensis* up to the nostril. Pupil was rounded in all but semicircle in *H. typhehensis*; tongue was pyriform in *E. cyanophlyctis* and *H. tigerinus* but bifid at the tip in *F. limnocharis* and *H. typhehensis*. Vomerine teeth were present and hind limbs were overlapped in all species. All the measured taxonomic parameters were positively correlated with snout to vent length.

Key words: Ranids, Taxonomic parameters.

Introduction

Amphibians are a class of vertebrate animals including frogs, caecilians, and salamanders. They are characterized as non-amniote ectothermic tetrapods (Wikipedia, 2009). Scientists have named approximately 1.75 million species of living organisms (Groom *et al.* 2006) where approximately 0.5% of all animal species measuring 6347 species (AmphibiaWeb, 2011) belong to the class Amphibia. Amphibians appeared in the late Devonian Period, about 350 million years ago (Minelli, *et al.*, 1987). Many fossil ranids are known, including both extant and extinct species of *Rana* from the Tertiary and Quaternary in Europe and North America, and probable *Ptychadena* fossils from the Miocene of Morocco (Heying, 2003). They are important in nutrient cycling between fresh waters and upland terrestrial environments, as pond nutrients, incorporated into their larval structure, are transported to the land through dispersal and death of transformed individuals (Storer and Usinger, 1972). From the agricultural point of view they are often referred to as farmer's Friend (Dutta and Mohanty, 1978). As the consumed foods of Amphibians are mostly of insects, so that they are very important of biological control of pests. On the other hand, they are eaten by predators such as fishes, snakes, birds, mammals (Blaustein and Wake, 1995). Thus the amphibians play an important role to equilibrate the ecosystems. Moreover, Amphibian species or communities have been touted as useful indicators in many situations (Welsh and Ollivier 1998, Galatowitsch *et al.* 1999, Collins and Storer 2003, Sheridan and Olson 2003, Hammer *et al.* 2004). Among the amphibian ones, the true frogs, family Ranidae, have the widest distribution of any frog family. They are abundant throughout most of the world, occurring on most continents except Antarctica. Typically, true frogs are smooth, moist-skinned frogs, with large, powerful legs and extensively webbed feet. The true frogs vary greatly in size, ranging from small—such as the Wood Frog (*Rana sylvatica*)—to the largest frog in the world, the Goliath frog (*Conraua goliath*) (Wikipedia, 2009). The members of this family having the features of toothed upper jaw; parotid glands are absent. Diapophyses of sacral vertebrae not but very slightly dilated (Boulenger, 1890). Ranids are Neobatrachians, but relationships among the families of these "advanced" frogs are almost wholly unresolved. Within the Neobatrachia, ranids are members of the superfamily Ranoidea, a clade of derived forms that likely loses its monophyly if Dendrobatidae is included. Family relationships among the ranoids are in a state of chaos, and should be considered unknown. The number of subfamilies described for Ranidae has fluctuated considerably over the years, coincident with new hypotheses of relationship (Heying, 2003). Hence it is very important to know the sharp differences among different taxonomic parameters to study a species thoroughly, to differentiate one species from others and to determine its original systematic position as well as to identify a new species. For convenience of observation only a few species were selected for study.

Materials and Methods

The research work was conducted at the laboratory of Department of Zoology, Jahangirnagar University during the period of March to December 2008. For this study the specimens were collected from the bank of ponds, lakes and other water bodies and from the wet-grassy area of various parts of Bangladesh. These were

collected mainly in the evening to 11 pm after a period of rain. At night torchlight was used in collection for illumination. Immediately after collection, the date, time, place of collection, local name, habitat type, color, species no. and individual no. were recorded with a tag in bottle and plastic and glass zars in the laboratory of Zoology Department of Jahangirnagar University. During the time of amphibian's collections some photographs were also collected for clear justification of the study. After capturing the specimens, these were killed by chloroform and preserved in either 5-10% formalin or 30-40% alcohol.

Methods of identification : All the collected amphibian species were identified through taxonomic keys as stated follows-Dorsal fold, Longitudinal fold, Supra-tympanic, Dorsal color, Ventral color, Head length (HL) in mm, Head width (HW) in mm, Inter-orbital width (IOD) in mm, Diameter of tympanum (TYD) in mm, Diameter of tympanum from eye (DBET) in mm, Snout to vent length in mm (SVL), Relative study of toe, Relative study of finger, Degree of webbing, Pupil shape, Tongue shape, Vomerine teeth, Overlapping of hind limb, Tibio-tarsus articulation, Discs of digits, Parotid gland and Warts on the body.

Methods of Data Analysis: For data analysis some statistics like measures of variability such as range, standard deviation etc. and correlation coefficient were done. Variability being a biological characteristic, no single measurement or observation of a variable is considered as an indicator of normality. A range defines the normal limits of a biological characteristic (Mahajan, 1997). Range can be measured as- $R = X_{(n)} - X_{(1)}$; Here, $X_{(n)}$ = The lowest observation in the series and $X_{(1)}$ = The highest observation in the series (Bhuyan, 2004).

To evaluate the variation of difference of an observation from the mean is by chance or real due to special reason. Actually it is used to have an idea of the precision of estimate (Bhuyan, 2004) which measured as-

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}, \text{ where } \mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i.$$

The relationship or association between two quantitatively measured or continuous variables is called correlation. The extent of degree or relationship between two sets of figures is measured in terms of another parameter called correlation co-efficient (Mahajan, 1997). It can be measured as-

$$r = \frac{\sum XY - \frac{\sum X \sum Y}{N}}{\sqrt{(\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N})(\sum Y^2 - \frac{(\sum Y)^2}{N})}}$$

Results and Discussion

***Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis* (Schneider, 1799), Indian skipper frog: (Fig. A)**

Color: Some were (n=24) greyish, some (n=7) blackish and some were brown dorsally, dark spotted, with many small tubercles. But all of them were white ventrally. Boulenger, 1890 found tubercles but colour was brown or olive above, beneath often speckled with blackish.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds, longitudinal folds and supra-tympanic were present; relative length of fingers were 3>4>1>2 and toes were 4>3>5>2>1; digits were fully webbed but without discs; pupil was rounded whereas tongue was pyriform; vomerine teeth present; tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to eye which is similar to Boulenger, 1890; hind limbs were not overlapped.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters are given below in the Table 1. All these parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.85735, HW 0.91332, IOD 0.89839, TYD 0.80604 and DBET 0.93093).

Table 1. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	38.7875	± 11.4276	27.4 to 59
HL	13.4625	± 4.08339	8.6 to 21.7
HW	11.2	± 3.58489	7.1 to 18.7
IOD	3.55	± 1.13011	2.3 to 5.2
TYD	3.6875	± 2.43277	2 to 9.5
DBET	11.7375	± 2.38563	8.6 to 15.2

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

***Fejervarya limnocharis*, Cricket Frog (Fig. B)**

Color: The specimens of this species found in BLRI were variable in color. Some were (n=5) brown, some (n=3) blackish and some were greyish dorsally; some with white mid-dorso-line, some without any mid-line. But all of them were white ventrally. Boulenger, 1890 found this species greenish or olive, with darker spots.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds, longitudinal folds and supra-tympanic were present; relative length of fingers were 4>3>1>2 and toes were 4>3>5>1>2; digits were half webbed but without discs; tibio-tarsus articulation reached beyond the eye; Boulenger, 1890 also found such result; pupil was rounded whereas tongue was bifid at the tip; vomerine teeth present; hind limbs were overlapped.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters were as shown in Table 2. All these parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.76415, HW 0.82688, IOD 0.62239, TYD 0.62109 and DBET 0.1851).

***Hylarana taipehensis*, Taipeh frog: (Fig. C)**

Color: All the specimens of this species were green dorsally and yellowish ventrally as cited in as IUCN, 2000.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds, longitudinal folds and supra-tympanic were absent; relative length of fingers were 4>3>2>1 and toes were 4>5>3>2>1; digits were fully webbed; discs of digits were present; vomerine teeth present; these are more or less similar to the IUCN, 2000; pupil was semicircle whereas tongue was bifid at the tip; hind limbs were overlapped; tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to the nostril.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters are given in the Table 3. All these parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.998453, HW 0.984984, IOD 0.986214, TYD 0.988388 and DBET 0.999648).

***Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* (Daudin, 1803) Indian bull frog: (Fig. D)**

Color: All the specimens of this species were olive-green with an only exceptional greenish dorsally.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds, longitudinal folds and supra-tympanic were present; relative length of fingers were 3>1>2=4 and toes were 4>5>3>2>1; digits were fully webbed but without discs; vomerine teeth present; hind limbs were overlapped; tibio-tarsus articulation reached beyond the eye; Boulenger, 1890 also found such results; pupil was rounded whereas tongue was pyriform.

Table 2. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Fejervarya limnocharis*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	44.5917	± 13.3858	26.2 to 63
HL	16.9917	± 4.23287	12 to 28
HW	13.4917	± 3.4036	8 to 17.4
IOD	6.10833	± 1.73805	3.1 to 8.3
TYD	4.575	± 1.32536	2.1 to 7.5
DBET	4.925	± 3.04246	0.6 to 12.1

Table 3. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Hylarana taipehensis*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	40.1	± 6.65983	34.6 to 49.5
HL	15.775	± 3.20975	13.3 to 20.3
HW	11.4	± 2.1276	9.6 to 14.2
IOD	11.075	± 2.29547	9.1 to 14.1
TYD	8.15	± 1.17331	7.1 to 9.7
DBET	7.325	± 1.04043	6.5 to 8.8

Table 4. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	102.16	± 30.8117	65.6 to 140.5
HL	23.34	± 2.96193	21.1 to 28.4
HW	19.9	± 3.19922	17.3 to 25.4
IOD	4.32	± 0.69065	3.6 to 5.4
TYD	4.62	± 0.8167	3.8 to 5.5
DBET	4.88	± 0.54037	4.1 to 5.5

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters were as given in the Table 4. All these parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.82827, HW 0.76438, IOD 0.55855, TYD 0.09392 and DBET 0.54319).

A. *Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis*

B. *Fejervarya limnocharis*

C. *Hylarana taipehensis*

D. *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*

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